

Error Analysis of Student's Descriptive Text Writing Using Grammarly Software

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ABSTRACT

One of the English skills which is important to be mastered by students is writing skills. Writing is creative and expressive process. Students need to explore their ideas to write comprehensively. However, there are still many students who make mistakes in writing. This study aims to determine the types of errors most often made by students in writing descriptive text with Grammarly software. Qualitative research design was used in this study. Error analysis in student writing with Grammarly software was applied to 2 classes with a total of 20 English education students. This research is expected to provide valuable insights into good writing procedures, especially in descriptive text writing and the use of Grammarly (AI) software platforms in improving students' writing skills. The results of the research on error analysis and error classification with Grammarly software show that there are 4 errors made by students in writing descriptive text, namely correctness 46 (51%) errors, clarity 28 (31%) errors, engagement 11 (12%) errors and delivery 5 (6%) errors. With correctness 46 errors and clarity 28 errors as the most frequent types of errors made by students. These findings indicate that students need to improve their writing skills by utilizing the available Grammarly software platforms (AI).

ABSTRAK

Salah satu bagian penting dalam kehidupan akademis adalah menulis. Siswa akan menulis banyak hal, seperti menulis surat, esai, narasi, mengikuti ujian, dan lain sebagainya. Namun, tidak mudah untuk menguasai keterampilan ini, terutama ketika siswa harus belajar menulis dalam bahasa asing seperti bahasa Inggris. Keterampilan menulis memang sulit karena kegiatan ini membutuhkan proses berpikir yang kompleks dan sistematis, namun keterampilan ini perlu dikuasai oleh pembelajar bahasa Inggris. Keterampilan menulis dalam komunikasi juga penting untuk dikuasai. Manfaatnya akan terasa ketika bahasa tulis dipublikasikan dan dibaca oleh banyak orang. Maka dari itu, kualitas tulisan harus selalu ditingkatkan. Bagi banyak siswa yang belajar bahasa Inggris sebagai bahasa kedua (ESL) atau sebagai bahasa asing (EFL), menulis dalam bahasa Inggris telah menjadi suatu tugas (Fathia Baresh, 2022). Kondisi ini juga terjadi di sekolah menengah atas bahkan perguruan tinggi.

INTRODUCTION

According to (La Oni, 2022), thirteen text types were studied by University students: narrative, descriptive, retelling, report, explanation, process, discussion, analytical exposition, hortatory, news, review, spoof, and anecdote. The researcher focused on the descriptive text that is taught to college students. As stated above, the explanatory text is taught by introducing the students to the model text, hoping they can write the genre well.

Significantly, writing in Indonesian and English has many differences in structure, spelling, syntax, and other aspects. This is one of the factors that cause writing errors students make in the learning stage. According to (Firmansyah, 2022), an incorrect response is considered an error since the student needs to know the correct answer. Errors in writing cause readers to have difficulty understanding the content of the writing and will lose the intended message in writing. Errors in the learning process are a natural thing for students to do. Therefore, it becomes essential to analyze their writing errors.

Errors are natural in the learning process. So, it is imperative to analyze their errors. According to (Rahma Hakiki, 2021). The Grammarly app helps writers and EFL students write. People stated that Grammarly is not a translation tool because it deals with grammatical aspects; the fact is that this software could be a tool to improve students' translation quality by giving grammatical feedback and proofreading services for the translator.

This study aims to improve students' writing skills, especially in writing descriptive texts by utilizing technology (AI) in the form of Grammarly to support students' writing skills so as to minimize the occurrence of errors in student writing. The results of this study are expected to make a significant contribution to the development of technology-based learning methods that can be integrated into the formal education system, especially in improving students' skills in writing texts.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Error Analysis

According to (Khansir 2012), error analysis is a type of linguistic analysis that focuses on student errors. Error analysis also emphasizes how students make errors in their second language. This is very important because interference caused by students' mother tongue is not the only reason errors are made in the target language. (Karim et al. 2018) state that error analysis is a method for systematically identifying, classifying, and interpreting unacceptable patterns made by students learning a foreign language.

These errors result in incorrect writing or speech, which the students need help to correct. At the previous research site, some students also needed to improve their writing text in English (Gayo & Widodo, 2018). Errors can also occur when students need help understanding structural grammar or the rules of a foreign language. In addition, a learner's progress in learning a language can be seen through errors. This allows teachers to improve language teaching and learning, especially in writing.

Error Classification

Error classification is necessary to investigate and describe students' errors. (Dulay. et al. 1982) present several different error categories according to several errors learners produce in acquiring a language. Those categories are linguistic category taxonomy, surface strategy taxonomy, comparative category taxonomy, and communicative effect taxonomy.

Descriptive Text

Descriptive text conveys meaning through sensory details and gives the reader a picture. In addition, paragraphs, consisting of interconnected sentences with a single purpose of commentary, are often used to describe a person's appearance. Descriptive writing vividly describes a person, location, or object so the reader can visualize the subject and enter the writer's experience. It enhances other types of writing or is a dominant method of creating an understanding of what something is like. Descriptive text is one of the types of writing; this type of writing aims to describe a particular person, animal, place, or even thing, which mainly describes the features and characteristics. Descriptive text is highlighted when you describe someone or something; you give your readers a picture in words. Descriptive texts differ from others because they describe objects using careful details to impress the reader.

Descriptive texts usually also use the present simple tense. To make teaching and learning descriptive text writing more interesting, teachers should. (Masitoh et al., 2015) state that descriptive text describes a person, place, or thing through visual experience. Furthermore, descriptive texts are divided into two paragraphs: objective and subjective. Objective paragraphs describe the topic literally and impartially. As much as possible, the writer's feelings are not expressed. This type of paragraph includes words that do not convey high emotions. Descriptive writing is the realm of writing that develops images through the precise use of sensory words and phrases and devices such as metaphors and word sounds. (Agustina & Muklas, 2018) They stated that the general structure of descriptive text consists of identification and description. Students must explain the object's components, features, and qualities in the description component. Sometimes, students need to organize paragraphs well. In organizing ideas, students should pay attention to the text in chronological order in addition to the identification and description elements. Chronological order is a time-based order that explains processes and events within a certain period.

Grammarly Software

In 2009, Shevchenko, Lytvyn, and Lider created the Grammarly app to check writing in articles or papers. The app can also correct English writing to conform to English grammar or grammar rules and check spelling in language structures.

(Perdana & Farida, 2019) State that checking and editing grammar is essential to writing. It is used in situations where other language materials are needed. In other words, it is used when teachers need help finding information from other print or online resources. One of them is Grammarly, which you can try and use at <https://www.grammarly.com/> to help you tackle spelling, grammar, punctuation, and other errors you may encounter while writing. According to (Fitria, 2021), Grammarly has two features: individual (free and premium version) and team (business version).

English grammar checking using Grammarly requires an internet connection (data plan) and by using some online grammar-checking services. Users will find two service options, namely, the use of free

and paid features. Individuals can use the free features, while the paid features can be used on a 'premium' and 'business' basis. Grammarly software has some features that can correct and analyze the students' errors, such as correctness, clarity, engagement, delivery.

Correctness

One of Grammarly's true features is correctness the ability to correct grammar, spelling, and punctuation. This feature will detect and explain grammatical errors in our writing. It will also provide suggestions to help you present the right, re-readable words for our writing.

Clarity

In writing, just because a sentence is grammatically correct does not mean it is easy to follow. Because when someone writes a text or essay, they are often unclear or use a lot of repetition of words to explain something. As a result, the purpose of grammar software is to make writing easier to understand. And the part of kinds are hard-to-read and wordy

Engagement

Even if the idea is good or the grammar is perfect, uninteresting writing will hurt both the writer and the reader. Readers won't get bored after the first paragraph. So, use Grammarly software to make your writing more specific, clear, and interesting to keep your readers engaged. Variety, vocabulary, and monotonous passages are the types of engagement Grammarly software provides.

Delivery

Delivery conveys the literal sense of the words used, transmission transmits a lot of information. It is particularly important to get the delivery correct in writing, because we can not rely on the voice of facial expressions to project authenticity, trust, and politeness. Delivery in Grammar software to make the best impression of writing formality, trust, friendliness.

Plagiarism

Nowadays, most students don't like fuss and just want it simple. Therefore, they may just copy and paste from the internet or books. This feature is very useful for checking student plagiarism as it can detect it.

METHODS

Research Design

This research uses descriptive qualitative research. (Sugiyono 2010) states that qualitative research methods are used to study the conditions and results of natural objects with more emphasis on meaning than generalization. Researchers use this type of research because the aim is to describe the phenomenon using the scientific method, with the actual circumstances in the form of scientific words using a descriptive approach.

In this research, the researcher uses a descriptive method design, which is a research method that aims to describe and interpret objects as they are. This is done because the data analysis is presented descriptively. Like other qualitative research approaches, qualitative descriptive studies are generally characterized by simultaneous data collection and analysis (Lambert, 2012). Descriptive qualitative research is a method for investigating the status of a group of people to create an object, such as a painting or photograph, in a systematic, factual, and accurate way about the phenomenon or fact being investigated.

Population comprises all students in the second-semester English Education program at Gorontalo University. The reason the researchers chose this semester as the population for the study is because semester 2nd students get a writing course after graduating from the intensive course, namely the WRITING FOR PROFESSIONAL CONTEXT course; one of the materials from this course is a descriptive text, which requires students to write an essay as an assignment from the course. The researcher used purposive sampling method to collect two classes (classes 3B and 3F, consisting of 20 students) were selected as the samples because they met all the requirements of the study

Researchers used error analysis as a method of data analysis in this study. The first step was to collect data from the results of the descriptive text written by 2nd-semester students majoring in English Education. After the researcher gets the student's writing, the researcher analyzes the student's writing using Grammarly software, error analysis is used by researchers as a method. There are several steps in applying the error analysis method in analyzing data. The first step in conducting an error analysis is to collect data in this study, obtained from students' Essay writing results. The second step, error identification refers to the identification of mistakes students make in writing. After the error is identified, the next step is to classify it into the type. Errors were discovered through the identification of classification in Grammarly software (Correctness, Clarity, Engagement, delivery, Plagiarism).

RESULT

Table 1. Types of Errors in Student Essay Writing Using Grammarly Software

Type of Error	Frequency	Percentage
Correctness	46	51%
Clarity	28	31%
Engagement	11	12%
Delivery	5	6%
Plagiarism	0	0

Based on table 1 above the frequency and percentage type of error using Grammarly software, the researcher found 90 errors in the second-semester student's descriptive text in English Language Education Study Program at Gorontalo State University. The researcher found 46 errors of Correctness type, 28 errors of Clarity type, 11 errors of Engagement type, 5 errors of Delivery type, and 0 errors of plagiarism.

DISCUSSION

This study presents the findings (errors) found during the research which are found in 20 descriptive text writing results by students in classes E and F with Grammarly software. In this section, the researcher found that there are four types of errors contained in the results of students' descriptive writing with Grammarly software, namely; correctness, clarity, engagement, and delivery

In summary, after analyzing 20 descriptive texts written by students with Grammarly software, the author found several errors made by students (46 correctness errors, 28 clarity errors, 11 engagement errors, and 5 delivery errors). Based on these results, the total of all errors in this study classified into four categories (correctness, clarity, engagement, and delivery) is 90 errors. Thus, the research question has been answered through the results of students' descriptive text writing with Grammarly software written by 20 students majoring in English education in classes E and F are correctness, clarity, engagement, and delivery. The researcher also found the most frequent types of errors made by students in writing, namely correctness as 46 errors and clarity as 28 errors.

Factors That Cause Students to Make Errors (Correctness, Clarity, Engagement, and Delivery) in Writing Descriptive Texts.

The errors made by students in the aspects of correctness, clarity, engagement, and delivery show that writing is a complex skill that requires mastery of various language elements at once. Factors such as weak grammar mastery, limited vocabulary, lack of creative writing practice, and not understanding the audience play a major role in the emergence of these errors.

CONCLUSION

The researcher analyzed writing errors made by 2nd semester students majoring in English Education at Gorontalo State University, there were 4 errors made by students in descriptive essays based on the results of analysis with Grammarly software namely correctness, clarity, engagement, and delivery. Correctness is the highest error that researchers found in this study while clarity error is in the second position frequent error made by students in writing, and engagement error is in the third position, and delivery is the lowest error in this study. However, in this study, researchers did not find plagiarism errors. This indicates that students still have many problems or lack of understanding of good and correct writing procedures. From the above results, it can be concluded that Grammarly software can identify students' errors in writing descriptive essays.

Therefore it is important for students to understand the structure and function of grammar and continue to learn so that they can reduce the occurrence of writing errors again in a writing, especially in writing English texts.

After presenting the results of the study, the researcher has some suggestions for students, teachers, and researchers provide some suggestions for students, teachers or lecturers, and future researchers. For students who are still learning English and also students who are studying in the English education department, researchers recommend that an understanding of English grammar is needed because, as students majoring in English education, a deep understanding of each part of the English language is needed, including grammar. In addition, for English teachers or lecturers, especially grammar and writing, to pay more attention to students' awareness, and provide more treatment to improve their ability in writing, especially in mastering grammar.

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